

Research and Issues Related to through Restoration of the Gospel in Japan: Joseph Hardy Niijima & Goro Takahashi's lives and Relationship with The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints

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Abstract

This paper introduces Joseph Hardy Niijima & Goro Takahashi are well-known scholars of Bible studies and translators of various scriptures. They had considered helping to understand the Bible, doctrines, and history of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, as well. The papers use apt literature reviews from online and offline media sources and use qualitative research methodology to get results. The paper establishes that all people on this earth, despite of any intellectual or religious background, have the same opportunities to obtain the doctrines of salvation through family historical research and temple ordinances from their ancestors.

Keywords: Research, Issues, Gospel, Japan, Joseph Hardy Niijima & Goro Takahashi, The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints.

1. Introduction

This paper introduces Joseph Hardy Niijima and Goro Takahashi who are known scholars of Bible studies and translators of various scriptures. This may help us understand the background of the restoration of the Gospel in the early years in Japan. This paper discusses his works of ways of seeking truth in spirituality and applying our time.

2. Methodology of the study

The main method used in writing this study was a literature review of online and offline media sources, assisted by qualitative research methodology. A review and summary of important research sources, articles, reports, and books on the topics were undertaken.

3. Joseph Hardy Neesima's Life

Joseph Hardy Neesima was born on February 12, 1843 (January 14, Tenpo 14) - January 23, 1890 (Meiji 23)). He was a Christian and educator from the end of the Edo period to the Meiji period. His birth name was Shimeta, and his given name was Keikan. In 1864 (Genji 1) during the Edo period, he secretly left the country and travelled to the United States, where he was baptized as a Christian and studied at Phillips Academy (high school), Amherst College, and Andover Theological Seminary. He then became a quasi-missionary for the American Board, a Congregationalist evangelistic organization that descended from the Puritan movement of the Reformed Church (Calvinism). After returning to Japan in 1875 (Meiji 8), Niijima founded Doshisha English School (later Doshisha University) in Kyoto Prefecture with the help of the American Board. In November 1860, he entered the Shogunate's Naval Training School, where he studied navigation, English, mathematics, and other subjects. In September 1862, he applied to the domain to become a disciple of Koga Gengo and learn Western military science, surveying, and arithmetic, which was granted. Around this time, he read the RenpoShiryaku and was shocked to learn about the presidential

system of the United States. One day, he came across a Chinese translation of the Bible translated by an American missionary, and decided to “go to a country where the gospel is taught freely.” Nijijima decided to travel abroad, which was prohibited at the time.

4. Joseph Hardy Nijijima and The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints

According to Nijijima’s journal on Oct 26, 1826, Nijijima called on Brigham Young at his office. On account of his illness, he could not see him, but his secretary entertained him. The secretary introduced him to Elder Orson Pratt, one of their Twelve apostles, and the ablest man among them. Nijijima met Elder Prett at the Historian's office, and he had talked with Elder Pratt for nearly two hours. Elder Pratt told Nijijima the chief doctrine of Mormonism. Afternoon Elder Pratt took Nijijima to their university for half an hour. Then Nijijima visited the Tabernacle. That is in a tremendous building. The Mormons themselves made the size of the organ in Boston Music Hall. Nijijima noticed the house was decorated with sagebrush etc. The Church believes in God and eternal Father in his son Jesus Christ as the Savior of the world. All mankind has to repent for sin and anything evil. They can be baptized in water, important for the remission of sins. They have the promise of laying on hands by the Holy Ghost. Holy Ghost will enlighten the mind. Through its gift and power sick will be healed, the blind will see, the deaf hear and the lame walk. There will be a resurrection of all that is faithful from the dead. It is from about 1827. It was revealed to Joseph Smith by an angel of God. Golden plate that book was written in ancient times by forefathers in the West Indies in America. They had prophets among them who wrote out records. Saints will receive our doctrine and will be gathered from all nations into one place.

On the American continent, they will build a great city on the Western border of the state of Missouri. The city will be called Zion or New Jerusalem and at the same time the Jews will rebuild in Palestine in Asia and all nations on this land and another country who do not repent will perish by wars and famines and pestilences and lastly by devouring fire. This is the beginning of 1000 years of rest. During that period the whole earth will be filled with the glory of the Lord. 1. The Book of Mormon; 2. The Book of Doctrine and Covenant and 3. Voice of warning. 1st President was appointed by an angel of God, to be Apostle to preside over the [church?]. Mr. Joseph Smith from his apostle, was bestowed upon. Inspiration Pt Mr. B. Young was ordained by Mr. Smith. Two counsellors were selected and sustained by the united voice of the people. Each Mormon must receive revelation. On the latter day, all will prophesy. Twelve Apostles were appointed by revelations and ordained by the coming of the Lord. Prophet Isaiah in his prophecy. Zion will be built which is written in the diary. (Nijijimajōzenshūhenshūinkai 1985; 1996)

5. Goro Takahashi and the Bible

Takahashi Goro (高橋五郎 April 24, 1856 (March 20, 1856) - September 7, 1935) was a translator, enlightened English literature scholar, English scholar, linguist, critic, and educator from the Meiji period to the early Showa period. He translated the Bible taught English, and served as a professor at Rikkyo University, Waseda University, and Komazawa University. He was born in 1856 (Ansei 3) to a village headman's family in Kashiwazaki, Echigo Province. His real name was 吾良 Goro. In 1868, he went to Takasaki, Gunma Prefecture, and studied Chinese and Buddhist studies under Ichikawa Sakon at Ryumonji Temple. From 1871, he studied under Makino Sairyu and Tanaka Keno at the Takasaki Domain School. In 1873, he went to Tokyo to study Western studies and studied under Ogata Koretaka (Ogata Jojiro, the third son of Ogata Koan) at the Ogata School, where he became acquainted with Uemura Masahisa. In 1875 (Meiji 8), he went to Yokohama, and through

Uemura's introduction, he studied English, English, French, and German at the Brown School of S. R. Brown, a missionary of the Dutch Reformed Church in America. Samuel Robbins Brown (June 16, 1810 - June 20, 1880), a missionary of the Dutch Reformed Church in America, learned the English alphabet and English, French, and German at Brown School. He was born on June 16, 1810, in East Windsor, Connecticut, to Timothy Brown, a machinist, and Phebe Brown, a hymn writer. When he was three years old, his family moved to Ellington, and then to Monson, Massachusetts, when he was eight. Around this time, he attended the Congregational Church with his mother and enrolled in Monson Academy (now Wilbraham & Monson Academy). Goro Takahashi was baptized by Brown, and from 1874 (Meiji 7), he helped with the translation of the Meiji 1st Translation of the Bible, which Brown had begun. When Brown returned to Japan in 1879 (Meiji 12), he contributed to the translation of the Old and New Testaments as an assistant to J. C. Hepburn.

James Curtis Hepburn (March 13, 1815 - September 21, 1911) was a medical missionary and physician for the Presbyterian Church in the United States. He visited Japan at the end of the Edo period, engaged in medical activities in Yokohama, and was also involved in translating the Bible into Japanese as a pastor. Hepburn is known for compiling the first Japanese-English dictionary, *Wagai Rinshusei*, which popularized the Hepburn romanization system, and made a great contribution to the advancement of English studies. In Tokyo, he also contributed to higher education by founding Meiji Gakuin (now Meiji Gakuin High School and Meiji Gakuin University) and becoming its first prime minister. In Tokyo, he founded Meiji Gakuin (now Meiji Gakuin High School and Meiji Gakuin University) and became its first prime minister, contributing to higher education. In 1867 (Keio 3), Hepburn compiled and published Japan's first Japanese-English dictionary, *Wagai Rinshusei*. The first edition was published under the name "Amerika Heibun (Bikoku Hei-bun)." Goro Takahashi passed away in September 7, 1935 (Showa 10). His posthumous translation of the "Sei Korankyo" was published in collaboration with Aruga Amasi in 1938 (Showa 13). He was a man of many literary talents and also wrote books on English education. His grave is in Tama Cemetery (5-2-5). Goro Takahashi took part in a project to translate the Bible into Japanese, and assisted in revising Hepburn's "Japanese and English Hayashi Shusei." In 1892 (M25) he criticized Tetsujiro Inoue's paper on the exclusion of Christianity with Masahisa Uemura and others. He is known for his translations of books such as "The Heroes of Blutarch" and "Carlyle's History of the French Revolution," and has also written books on English education. In 1925 (T14) Goro Takahashi worked as a professor at Komazawa University. The series of "clairvoyance" riots from the end of the Meiji period to the beginning of the Taisho period reflected the process by which spiritual science was being excluded from scientific academia. However, the Taisho period was also a time when spiritualism was widely spread throughout the world, linking it with various ideological trends. Although it maintained a delicate distance from scientific academia, it still maintained a special circulation within it. It was also during this period that spiritualism began to integrate with various new religions, spiritual arts, etc., providing a theoretical background. This approach to spiritual science seems to have given a special shadow to Taisho writers such as Ryunosuke Akutagawa and Yoshio Toyoshima.

6. Goro Takahashi and The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints

This gives you a little idea of this man. I afterwards told my interpreter what he said. "Well, Mr. Grant", he said, "I told you that I could not interpret the article. I told you that it was like a rugged mountain. I told you it was so full of force and fire that I could not put it in the English language." The minute I read this article, I sent the writer an invitation to come

and dine with me at the hotel. He came there, and afterwards, he wrote and said, if I would furnish him items of history regarding our people, he would gladly write a book in our defence. He said, "I feel that you are honest, I feel that you are misunderstood, I feel that the Spirit of the Lord has come upon me, and I want to defend you, and if you will give me the materials I will do it; for I feel that I am called to this work." I immediately told him that it would give me pleasure. I furnished him the *History of Joseph Smith* by Brother Cannon, the *History of John Taylor* by Brother Roberts, and *A Brief History of the Church* by Edward H. Anderson. The latter is published by the Juvenile Instructor and does not give Brother Anderson the credit of being the author, but he is entitled to it, and if I could write such a work I would not let them publish it if they did not put my name upon it. I furnished him with *Mormon Doctrine* by Brother Penrose, *The New Witness for God* and *The Missouri Persecutions* by Brother Roberts, and the *Book of Mormon*. He already had the *Book of Mormon* and was pretty well posted on it. I also furnished him, among other documents, a tract by Colonel Thomas, of London, that impressed him very much. He has written a book of some 200 or more pages, about the size of the Improvement Era. He has illustrated it with pictures from the little pamphlet entitled "In and Around Salt Lake City." There is a picture there of the five presidents of the Church, also of the Temple block, a view of Salt Lake City, of Saltair, of the Salt Palace, and some Indians, with their children on their backs the same as the Japanese. And, by the way, there is a wonderful resemblance between the American Indian and many of the Japanese.

The pictures of Prest. Smith, of my family, and some others will be published in this book. He says that these pictures will dispel at a glance the popular idea that the "Mormons" are ignorant and degraded people. He has put in a picture of the Lehi sugar factory, and he was wonderfully impressed with what our people had accomplished materially. He said, "I may, of course, make a mistake in some of your doctrinal items. I would not like to do that. I may make a mistake in some of your historical items. I would not like to do that, either; and I shall submit to you the doctrinal and historical items before I publish my book." I invited him to dinner regularly every Sunday for about two months, and afterwards, he said he did not wish to show me anything in the book, because, he said, "people will say you told me what to write, and it will not do you the good I want it to do. I am writing in your favour, and I know you will be pleased with the book." He had read all Dr. Talmage's articles published in the Era on the "History and Philosophy of Mormonism," and he said that if he quoted the doctrinal and historical items from what I had given him he could not make any mistake, and that was what he had done. I am sorry I did not bring with me the contents of that book. It will contain 10 chapters, and the first is entitled "The Greatest Problem of the "World." This will give you some idea of what the man thinks. In the article he wrote about the "Mormons" before I ever met him, he wound it up by saying, "I will ask some questions. Was Joseph Smith a deceitful hero, who deceived the world, and was punished by the Almighty for his wickedness? Or was he, like Jesus Christ, a martyr for the truths of heaven?" I believe that this man became convinced that Joseph Smith was a martyr. Here is a list of the headings of the ten chapters:

Chapter I. The Greatest Problem in the World.

Chapter II. Mormonism—What is it? Early History of Joseph Smith.

Chapter III. The Book of Mormon, and American Antiquities; Archaeology and Comparative Philology.

Chapter IV. The Spaulding Story, and other Stories.

Chapter V. Exodus—Miracles—Chosen People.

Chapter VI. Phoenix-like, Risen out of the ashes.

Chapter VII. Loyal or Disloyal.

Chapter VIII. Polygamy. What is; it?

Chapter IX. Social Conditions. Social Christianity without running into Communism.

Chapter X. Success and Prosperity, Religious and Commercial.

Not one word that is in this book have I suggested, but I believe that I could not possibly pick out ten chapters and arrange them any better than this man has done. He is a highly educated man. He translated five-sevenths of the Bible into the Japanese language when it was done. He speaks the English language well; he speaks the Hebrew language, he understands some Egyptian, and he reads French. He has a two-story fireproof building adjoining his dwelling, full of books, where he studies. I have always looked upon Orson Pratt as the great student of the Latter-day Saints, and I remarked to my brethren that Goro Takahashi was the Orson Pratt of the Japanese nation. I feel that God touched this man's heart and made him friendly towards us, and he has written a book that I believe will do us a world of good. I remarked to him that I would like him to translate it into the English language and send it to me, and I would publish it at home, with the same illustrations, so that the people could see what he had written; that I knew it would have a good sale at home, and it would give me delight to let him have any profits that there might be. I told him that I realized it would take him a long time to translate it into the English language because he would not write as rapidly in our language as he could on his own. "You are very much mistaken," he said; "It won't take me very long, because there are so many exact quotations from the pamphlets and books you gave me. I have translated them into the Japanese language verbatim; therefore it won't be difficult to put them back into English." I feel that this man was raised by God to do this, and although he may have made some mistakes I believe his book will do us a great deal of good.

7. Goro Takahashi and the transition to spiritualism

In the preface to "The Current State of Spiritual Philosophy", Takahashi explains that "spiritual philosophy" "originated from modern spiritualism, which was revived in America in the mid-nineteenth century, and made rapid progress as a result of the emergence of many masters, but with the outbreak of World War, it became even more popular and was welcomed by the world as a powerful philosophy of comfort." As is already clear from the choice of the term "spiritual philosophy", spiritual science for Takahashi is, first of all, "philosophy." This does not mean that Takahashi's focus on spiritual science was limited to philosophy. Although it comes later than "The Current State of Psychic Philosophy," in "Ghostly Spiritual Communication," Vol. 109, Kobundo, Takahashi explains "psychic philosophy" as follows. Specific examples of "underworld communication" that Takahashi cites in "The Current State of Psychic Philosophy" include Swedenborg's "Heaven and Hell", William Stead's "Underworld Communication", and Oliver P. Lodge's "Raymond". He considers the worldwide attention to these so-called "underworld communications" to be a phenomenon brought on by World War I (Ichiyonagi 1996). As an attempt, let's take a look at the "Chronology of Psychological Literature in the Meiji Period," compiled in "Historical Materials on the Development of Mind-Embedded Science in the Meiji Period, "Psychological Research," edited by the Tokyo Psychological Research Group. The number of titles listed here is 243. Among them are 22 hypnotism books and 9 psychic books listed. Additionally, the list of spiritual books is concentrated after 1902. There are 62 psychology books published since 1909. Approximately 15% of these were spiritual books. Even into the

Taisho era, one of the elements that remained barely connected to proper psychology was the consideration of hypnosis and dreams. The study of dreams and hypnosis as materials and methods for examining “consciousness” has attracted sustained interest from both psychics and psychology. For example, “The Current State of Spiritual Philosophy” lists “Reimu Zuimu” as a means of “ghost transportation.” They focus on phenomena such as so-called prophetic dreams as one of how spirits communicate with us. Here, he says, “Spirits cannot speak directly to humans in physical reality, but by borrowing dreams and illusions, they can easily achieve the same goal.” What is interesting about “The Current State of Psychic Philosophy” is its perspective on spiritual arts. After giving an overview of the “clairvoyance incident,” and pointing out the persecution of “clairvoyance” in science, Takahashi states, “Many psychics had been smouldering in larceny without expressing their abilities publicly, but in the meantime, they had reached a ripe stage of evaporation, and craters were appearing here and there,” and he introduced several spiritual therapies that were popular in the world. Takahashi finds expression of new spiritual abilities in various spiritual arts and new religions, replacing the “clairvoyance” abilities of Chizuko Mifune and Ikuko Nagao. He had been paying attention to trends in new religions overseas, such as Christian Science and the Emmanuel movement, from an early stage, and discovered a similar phenomenon in Japan during the Taisho era. Below, he examines the state of metaphysical “techniques for manipulating matter,” in conjunction with the meaning of spiritual science based on metaphysical “philosophy.” From the way Takahashi looks at spiritual arts such as this one, we can see the Japanese style of transformation and absorption of spiritual science. Spiritual arts, which expanded and developed dramatically during the Taisho period, incorporated various ideas as their theoretical background. In this context, the effective use of the spiritual system of thought can function strategically in terms of differentiating itself from other spiritual organizations. Besides, from the perspective of those on the spiritual science side who wish to popularize the ideas of spiritual science, the popularity of spiritual arts can be seen as a part of concrete activities that demonstrate the validity of spiritual science.

8. Conclusion

Niijima is said to be the first Japanese person to obtain a degree from a Western institution of higher education. He continued to study to become a missionary, and in September of the following year, 1875 (Meiji 8), he passed the missionary candidate exam and became a missionary. Goro Takahashi did work from the end of the Meiji period to the Taisho period, systematic study of the doctrines and history of Islam was carried out, and in this context, Kenichi Sakamoto’s “Koran Kyo” (1920) was published by the World Sacred Works Publishing Association as the 14th volume “Koran 1” and the 15th volume “Koran 2” of the 30 volumes of the World Sacred Works (Azuma 1998). After that, Japan began to attach importance to Islam to expand into Asia, and Islamic research institutes such as the Institute for Islamic Studies were established. Under these circumstances, Goro Takahashi and Amado Ariga (Bunhachiro Ariga) co-translated “Seikorankei Islamic Canon” (1938) was published. All people on this earth, regardless of academic or religious background, have the same opportunities to receive the doctrines of salvation through family history research and temple ordinances for their ancestors.

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